

“DEVELOPMENT OF SOLAR OPERATED IOT BASED MULTIPURPOSE AGRI ROBOT”

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Abstract

The agricultural sector plays a crucial role in ensuring food security and sustainable development. To enhance agricultural efficiency and address labour shortages, the integration of advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and robotics has become imperative. This abstract presents a Solar Operated IoT-Based Multi-Purpose Agricultural Robot designed to cater to various agricultural tasks, ensuring optimal resource utilization and improved yield. The proposed robot is equipped with solar panels to harness renewable energy, making it environmentally friendly and cost-effective. The integration of IoT enables real-time monitoring, data collection, and control of the robot through a centralized system, allowing farmers to manage their fields efficiently. The design and development of a solar-powered multipurpose agriculture robot with IoT-based technology offer a transformative solution to the challenges facing modern farming practices. This abstract provides a comprehensive overview of the key components, functionalities, and potential applications of this innovative agricultural tool.

Keywords: smart farming, Internet of Things, sensors.

I. Introduction

The solar-powered multipurpose agriculture robot utilizing IoT technology is a revolutionary innovation poised to transform modern farming practices. This cutting-edge robot seamlessly integrates renewable energy and advanced connectivity to optimize various agricultural tasks, enhancing efficiency, sustainability, and productivity across the agricultural sector. At its core, this innovative robot harnesses the power of solar energy to drive its operations, significantly reducing reliance on traditional energy sources and minimizing the carbon footprint associated with agriculture. Equipped with high-efficiency solar panels, the robot autonomously charges itself during daylight hours, ensuring continuous operation even in remote or off-grid farming locations. By leveraging solar power, this agricultural robot offers a sustainable solution to

power-intensive farming operations, mitigating the environmental impact of conventional farming practices. One of the key functionalities of this agriculture robot is its ability to perform a wide range of tasks autonomously, relieving farmers of repetitive and labour-intensive activities. Equipped with precision tools and implements, the robot can undertake tasks such as soil cultivation, planting, irrigation, fertilization, and pest control with unparalleled accuracy and efficiency. By automating these tasks, the robot not only reduces the need for manual labour but also ensures consistent and optimized agricultural practices, ultimately leading to higher yields and improved crop quality. Moreover, the IoT-enabled features of this robot enable seamless integration with other smart farming technologies and systems, creating a holistic ecosystem for precision agriculture. For example, by interfacing with weather forecasting systems, the robot can adjust its operations in real-time based on upcoming weather conditions, optimizing irrigation schedules and crop management practices to maximize yield and minimize resource usage. Additionally, through cloud-based platforms, farmers can remotely monitor and control the robot's activities from anywhere, providing unprecedented flexibility and convenience in farm management. Another significant advantage of this solar-powered agriculture robot is its versatility and adaptability to diverse farming environments and crop types. Whether operating in large-scale commercial farms or smallholder plots, the robot can be customized and configured to meet specific requirements, offering scalability and flexibility to farmers of all scales. Furthermore, its modular design allows for easy upgrades and integration of new technologies, ensuring future-proof functionality and long-term value for farmers.

II. Literature

The most significant contributor to recent breakthroughs in technical development is machine learning. The solar-powered remote-operated multipurpose agricultural robot is engineered to perform a variety of farming tasks efficiently and remotely. By leveraging solar energy as its primary power source, the robot operates sustainably and autonomously, reducing the need for traditional energy sources and minimizing environmental impact. One of the key features of the robot is its remote-operated functionality, which allows farmers to control and monitor the robot's operations from a distance. This capability enhances flexibility and convenience, enabling farmers to manage farming tasks effectively even in remote or inaccessible areas. The robot is equipped with a range of tools and functionalities to support diverse agricultural activities, including ploughing, seeding, weeding, and spraying. Its multipurpose design enables farmers to streamline farming operations, optimize resource utilization, and improve

overall productivity. The main objective of the study is to create a multipurpose agricultural robot that can perform various tasks, such as ploughing, sowing seeds, and spraying pesticides, under remote control using a smartphone application. The robot is designed to navigate autonomously in the field and carry out tasks based on user commands received through the smartphone interface. The paper describes the hardware components and sensors integrated into the agricultural robot, including motors for movement, a seed dispenser mechanism, a pesticide sprayer, and an obstacle detection system. The robot's control system is based on an Arduino microcontroller, which receives instructions from the smartphone application via Bluetooth communication. The authors detail the software development process for both the smartphone application and the Arduino controller, emphasizing the user-friendly interface designed to enable farmers to operate the robot easily. They also discuss the implementation of obstacle avoidance algorithms to enhance the robot's navigation capabilities in the field. Overall, this research contributes to the advancement of agricultural robotics and underscores the potential of solar-powered autonomous systems in revolutionizing farming practices. The implications of this research are manifold. Firstly, the development of solar-operated IoT-based agriculture robots has the potential to revolutionize farming practices, particularly in regions facing agricultural labour shortages or limited access to conventional energy sources. By automating repetitive tasks and leveraging renewable energy, farmers can improve productivity, reduce operational costs, and enhance sustainability. Moreover, the adoption of IoT technologies enables precision agriculture, allowing for targeted interventions based on real-time data analysis. Looking ahead, there are several avenues for future research and development in this field. Firstly, further enhancements to the agriculture robot's capabilities could be explored, such as integrating advanced sensors for pest detection, weed management, and yield prediction. Additionally, research into the optimization of energy storage and management systems could improve the efficiency and reliability of solar-powered robots, particularly in regions with fluctuating weather patterns. Furthermore, there is a need for ongoing research into the socio-economic and environmental impacts of agriculture automation, including its implications for employment dynamics, land use patterns, and resource conservation. Collaborative efforts between academia, industry, and government agencies will be crucial in driving innovation and fostering the responsible adoption of agricultural robotics.

2.1 Methodology

The smart Agri robot is designed to carry out multiple tasks such as seed sowing, pesticide spraying, and Moisture sensor. As the solar panel absorbs sunlight and converts it into electricity, this energy is directed to a charging circuit which operates based on the maximum power point tracking (MPPT) protocol. A channel relay facilitates voltage supply to various mechanisms, while a motor driver is employed to operate the DC motors propelling the robot. Additionally, the model integrates an Android app and Bluetooth and Hotspot for signal transmission and reception respectively. The robot remains idle until it receives signals from the app, upon which it activates the designated operations accordingly. The prototype encompasses distinct output sections, effectively realizing the primary objective of the project. Figure illustrates the comprehensive prototype of the automated multipurpose robot, controllable via the accompanying app. It efficiently executes seed sowing, and pesticide spraying simultaneously across diverse farming landscapes.

Fig: 1 Methodology

Experimental Work

Parts Specification

Battery:

Fig.2 Battery Circuit

Sealed Rechargeable battery

AB 12V 7.2/12V-7.2 AH

Voltage Parameters

Constant Voltage Charge (27°C)

Cycle use: 14.1 V- 14.4 V

Max. Current; 1.4 A

ESP32 NODE-MCU CONTROLER:

Fig. 3 ESP32

Fig. 4 ESP32 Schematic

This is ESP WROOM 32 MCU Module. ESP WROOM 32 is a powerful, generic Wi-Fi-BT-BLE MCU module that targets a wide variety of applications, ranging from low-power sensor networks to the most demanding tasks, such as voice encoding, music streaming, and MP3 decoding. At the core of this module is the ESP32S chip, which is designed to be scalable and adaptive. There are 2 CPU cores that can be individually controlled or powered, and the clock frequency is adjustable from 80 MHz to 240 MHz.

The user may also power off the CPU and make use of the low-power coprocessor to constantly monitor the peripherals for changes or crossing of thresholds. ESP32S integrates a rich set of peripherals, ranging from capacitive touch sensors, Hall sensors, low-noise sense amplifiers, SD card interface, Ethernet, high-speed SDIO/SPI, UART, and I²C. In addition, this module can support data rates of up to 150 Mbps and 22 dBm output power at the PA in order to allow for the widest physical range.

<p>Application:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Universal low power IoT sensor hub. 2. Home automation. 3. Universal low power IoT recorder. 4. Wireless control. 5. OTT TV box / set-top box device. 6. Sensor networks. 	<p>Features:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Integrated 520 KB RAM. 2. Hybrid Wi-Fi & Bluetooth. 3. High level of integration. 4. On-board PCB antenna.
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Table.1: ESP32 Specification

Processor	Two Low-Power Xtensa 32-bit LX6 Microprocessors
Operating voltage (v)	3.0V – 3.6V
Operating current (mA)	80
Clock Frequency (MHz)	80 ~ 240
Flash memory (MB)	4
Data Rate (Mbps)	150
SRAM Memory (KB)	520
Length (mm)	28
Width (mm)	50
Height (mm)	14

Motors used:

Fig: 5 DC Wiper motor

Fig: 6 DC Motor

These motors open a wide choice for you in terms of wheels and chassis, specifications -,
 Rpm - 30,
 shaft diameter - 6mm (with internal hole).
 weight - 125gms, torque - 8 kg/cm.

voltage - 6 to 24 (nominal voltage - 12v).

no-load current = 60 ma (max).

load current = 300 ma (max).

	WM23 brushless motor	WM07C brushed motor			
Torque	45 Nm	25 Nm	30 Nm	35 Nm	40 Nm
Approximate dimensions (mm)					
	L	120	190		198
	H	90	76		79
Voltage	12 V				
Rotational speed Lo / Hi	40 rpm / 60 rpm	47 rpm / 67 rpm	45 rpm / 64 rpm		
Motor weight	790 g	760 g	770 g	800 g	870 g

*Characteristics during control operation

	WM23	WM07C			
		25 Nm	30 Nm	35 Nm	40 Nm
Maximum motor output	105 W	41 W	43 W	55 W	58 W

Solar panel:

Fig :7 Solar panel

Max. power pm :5.00Wp Open

circuit voltage :21.00v Max.

power current Isc:0.29A Max.

power voltage Vmp:17.00v Short

circuit Isc :0.30A

Max. System Voltage :600v

Calculation**Water pump:**

12-volt,

135 psi,

6 Liter per minute

Power consumption of pump is

$P = \text{Volt} * \text{amps}$

$P = 12 * 4 = 48W$

Solar Panel:

5 Watts of Panel

Solar panel output power = Watts * solar panel 1hr of sunshine * 0.85

$$= 5 * 1 * 0.85$$

$$= 4.25Wh$$

Battery:

12volts

7.2 Ah

Total available power from battery = volts* amps

$$= 12 * 7.2$$

$$= 86.4W$$

Motor:

Speed = 30 to 60 rpm

Voltage = 12volts

Amps = 4.2amps

Power Consumption of 1motor = volts *amps

$$= 12 * 4.2$$

$$= 50.4 W$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total power consumption of motor} &= 4 * \text{power} \\ &= 4 * 50.4 \\ &= 201.6\text{W} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Torque} &= \text{power} / 2 * \pi * \text{rpm} \\ &= 50.4 / 2 * \pi * 60 \\ &= 0.133\text{N-m} / \text{motor} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total Torque} &= 4 * \text{Torque} \\ &= 4 * 0.133 \\ &= 0.534 \text{ N-m} \end{aligned}$$

Total weight of model = 24 Kg.

2.2 Objectives

To design a IoT assisted Multipurpose agricultural robot aiming to address various challenges in modern agriculture with seed sowing, ploughing, irrigation and fertilizer. To develop a solar operated multipurpose agriculture smart robot to Reduce dependency on manual labor by automating repetitive and labor-intensive tasks, such as planting, weeding, and harvesting. To Implement precision agriculture techniques for precise and targeted application of resources, including water, fertilizers, and pesticides, leading to optimized use and reduced environmental impact.

2.3 Results and Discussion

An autonomous multipurpose agricultural robot is designed to perform the complex farming tasks like ploughing, seed sowing and pesticide spraying. The benefits of robot are reduced human intervention and efficient resources utilization. Instructions are passed to the system using Bluetooth which ensures no direct contact with human and thus safety of operator is ensured. The robot is solar powered hence it is renewable energy source. The operations are performed using android app. Innovative seed sowing, grass cutting and pesticide sprayer equipment has significant influence in agriculture. By using this advanced work, farmer can save more time and also reduce lot of labor cost. The use of conventional farming practices can have adverse effects on the environment, including soil erosion, depletion of natural resources, and the emission of greenhouse gases. Sustainable and eco-friendly alternatives are essential for the long-term health of the ecosystem.

III. Conclusion

The integration of solar power makes the robot environmentally sustainable and reduces reliance on conventional energy sources. This not only aligns with global efforts towards sustainability but also contributes to cost-effectiveness for farmers by utilizing renewable energy. The incorporation of IoT technology enables real-time monitoring, data collection, and centralized control. This facilitates precision agriculture, empowering farmers with insights into crop health, resource usage, and overall field management. The ability to make data-driven decisions can significantly enhance agricultural practices. The robot, with its IoT capabilities, empowers farmers with greater control and information about their fields. This connectivity allows for remote management, timely interventions, and improved decision-making, ultimately leading to enhanced productivity.

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